

TYPES OF SENTENCES FOR COMMUNICATIVE AIM IN THE SCIENTIFIC STYLE

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Abstract: The article discusses the types of sentences in scientific style. And it is touched upon in terms of expressiveness of sentences and their behavior in the composition of the text. As well as, it examines the types of expressiveness, reflecting openness to other texts and discourses, examines its specificity in scientific discourse, highlights its main functions and analyzes the types of sentences for communicative aims and the means of their implementation.

Key words: expressiveness, affirmative, interrogative, imperative, communicative aims, scientific style.

INTRODUCTION

Types of sentence according to the observed purpose, such as affirmative, interrogative and command, are used in all styles of speech. Each of these will have some specific signs, depending on their use in speech styles.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Affirmative sentences. Affirmative sentences are actively used in speech in relation to other types of sentences. Even an extensive text will consist only of affirmative sentences. Such sentences are used in the composition of all styles of speech. Texts on the style of scientific, official work papers consist mainly of affirmative sentences. In fiction, the landscape of nature, the portrait of images, their situational state are given through affirmative sentences.

It is known that when it is necessary to report an event or confirm or deny the existence of the subject sign, an affirmative sentence is addressed. In addition to the message, affirmative sentences also express additional meanings such as suspicion, joy, pity, longing, advice. The form of the predicate also plays an important role here, and the meanings in such a sentence are characteristic for the belles-lettres style [5]. The expression of affirmative sentences with meanings such as pity, longing is not characteristic of scientific works.

The judgment becomes clear in the affirmative sentences used in the scientific style. The texts of a monograph, textbook, popular science or scientific article are made almost from affirmative sentences, but, questioning in this scientific style, the command should not lead to the conclusion that sentences are not used at all.

Interrogative sentence. In the scientific style, both interrogative and command sentences are sometimes referred to, but interrogative and command sentences are manifestations typical of the scientific style, and not all of their pragmatic manifestations are used in texts specific to this style.

In the scientific style, rhetorical interrogative sentences, interrogative-command sentences are not used at all. In it, interrogative sentences, the content of which is more general, are used. Interrogative sentences directed at a particular concrete individual taken do not apply [1]. The listener is not expected to respond to such statements, but, on the contrary, the author himself responds to it.

In the scientific style, interrogative sentences as a means of drawing the attention of the addressee-reader to one issue or another are much questioned.

A type of interrogation in the heuristic description is used. In it, the interrogation is directed not at the listener, but at the speaker himself [2; 8]. Therefore, the answer is also expected not from the listener, but from the speaker himself.

In the scientific style, rhetorical interrogative sentences are sometimes also referred to as methodological tools. These serve for the felt-exciting-painted feature of the style [9].

Interrogative sentences used in the scientific style can be divided into two types in terms of meaning:

1. A problematic scientific issue is thrown into the middle by interrogation. This aims to focus the reader's attention on the idea being stated, to interest the reader, to emphasize the correctness of the thought.
2. The question will be intended to bring a meaningful statement into discussion. In it, the thoughts in the way of the answer will be different, one will deny the other. Therefore, the interrogation is directed to everyone, and the answer is given by the author himself.

Interrogative sentences are typical for textbook-type types of scientific style. Such an interrogation will be addressed to the general, the answer will be resolved in the presence of both the speaker and the listener, in moderation, in harmony [7].

Interrogative sentences are divided according to their grammatical basis into simple (monopredicative) and compound (polypredicative) sentences. Simple interrogative sentences are used in the form of a cry and a spread [3]. A monopredicative (simple) interrogative sentence's lamentable form often consists of a single word, accompanied by interrogative expressions of pragmatic meanings such as fear, joy, surprise, disbelief. Certain sounds are also a cry simple sentence: can come in function. But their sentence status is determined by context – text. They are mainly found in dialogue. This type of simple sentence is not typical for scientific speech.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Interrogative sentences in a polypredicative (compound) description can be the same or different types of reporting according to the scope of the information. Each component of a uniform-news polypredicative interrogative sentence also makes interrogative meaningful. While one of the components of various habitual polypredicative interrogative sentences is that the interrogative is meaningful, the other is darak, the command becomes meaningful [4; 6]. These are interrogative sentences that are not characteristic of the scientific style.

Imperatives. Imperatives are also much more widely used in texts specific to certain areas of science and technology, such as mathematics, physics, chemistry. This is especially common in scientific texts, where various assignments are reflected.

Sometimes in disciplines such as mathematics, geometry, trigonometry, given in the proof of certain theorems, the section of the action takes the form in the 3rd person in the imperative mood.

CONCLUSION

In the scientific style, the proof is in the form of imperative in parentheses, since the proof is strong and they are also known as appendices such as ... расмга қаралсин, ... жадвалга қаралсин, ... бобга қаралсин which is considered an abundant private case inherent in the text of scientific discourse.

It seems that in the scientific texts of the Uzbek language, all communicative types of a sentence are applied in their own way, to one degree or another. While scientific statement mainly uses affirmative sentences, partial interrogative sentences, priority is also observed in the use of interrogative sentences in scientific-commissioned, scientific-educational literature.

REFERENCES

1. KHUDAYBERDIEVICH M.M. (2023). The Concepts of Text and Discourse in Linguistics. JOURNAL OF ADVANCED LINGUISTIC STUDIES.
2. Mukumov Makhmud Khudayberdievich. (2023). A BRIEF INSIGHT INTO INTERTEXTUALITY. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 414–420. Retrieved from <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/1099>
3. Мукумов, М. Х. (2021). INTERPRETATION OF THE TERMS WORLD MODEL, WORLDVIEW, IMAGE OF THE WORLD IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 4(2).
4. Xayrulloqizi, B. N. (2021). A Comparative Analysis of Metaphor in English Proverbs. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 1(2), 59–60. Retrieved from <http://www.inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/40>
5. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi. (2023). The Role of Concept in Linguistics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1(10), 50–53. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJRCS/article/view/1861>
6. Abduholiqovna Q. G. Preliminary study of uzbek hydronymy on the roots //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 7. – С. 215-218.
7. Safarova Dilarom Abdukadirovna. (2023). THE PROPER NOUNS IN THE LEXICO-SEMANTICAL SYSTEM OF THE LANGUAGE. *American Journal of Philological Sciences*, 3(11), 29–31. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume03Issue11-05>
8. Сафарова, Д. А. (2018). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТОПОНИМОВ В РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКИХ ЯЗЫКАХ. Гуманитарный трактат, (37), 26-27.
9. Axmedova Dildora Jo'raxon Qizi. (2023). SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HYDROTOPONYMS, ZOOMORPHIC AND ETHNOPONYMS IN GERMAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research*, 18, 257–259. Retrieved from <https://americanjournal.org/index.php/ajper/article/view/1533>
10. Akhmedova Dildora Jo'rakhan kizi Lutfulla Kholyirov. (2023). LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF OIKONIM AND HYDRONYMS IN THE GERMAN LANGUAGE. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*.

Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(6), 172–176.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8017468>

11. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi, Safarova Farida Normurotovna (2021). The Features of a Good Translator in Translating Medical Terms. Analytical journal of education and development, (2181-2624)
<https://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/ajed/article/view/526/505>

12. AXMEDOVA, A. (2023). NEMIS TILI FONETIK KOMPETENSIYASINI SHAKLLANTRIRISHDA INNOVATSION TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINING ROLI . Journal of Research and Innovation, 1(4), 42–45. Retrieved from <https://imfaktor.com/index.php/jorai/article/view/353>

13. Akhmedova Adolat Ravshan kizi. (2022). Problems of Formation of Phonetic Competence of Students (A Level 1). Eurasian Scientific Herald, 6, 160–162. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/esh/article/view/91>